

Research Article

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Determinants of Smallholder Farmers' Lablab Productivity in Northern and Central Tanzania

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Abstract: Lablab is an emerging legume crop with the potential to enhance food security and household incomes among smallholder farmers in Tanzania. However, productivity remains low due to agronomic, socio-economic, and institutional challenges. This study investigated determinants of lablab productivity among smallholder farmers in Arusha, Manyara, Singida, and Dodoma regions. A cross-sectional survey was conducted using structured questionnaires to collect quantitative data from 200 randomly selected households. Qualitative data were collected through key informant interviews and focus group discussions across all regions. Data were analysed using SPSS version 27, STATA MP version 17, and thematic analysis for qualitative data. Descriptive statistics profiled respondents, while ordinal logistic regression assessed variables influencing productivity levels. Findings revealed lablab production is predominantly male-led (74.5%), concentrated among middle-aged farmers with limited formal education. Most farmers cultivated lablab for commercial purposes, although productivity was constrained by pests and diseases (84.5%), limited access to quality seed (83%), high fertilizer costs (75.5%), and weather conditions (61.5%). Regression results showed improved seed use ($\beta = 3.575$, $p < 0.01$), crop rotation ($\beta = 2.318$, $p < 0.01$), effective pest and disease control ($\beta = 2.518$, $p < 0.05$), and favourable weather conditions ($\beta = 0.861$, $p < 0.05$) significantly associated with productivity. Conversely, fertilizer use showed a negative association ($\beta = -1.613$, $p < 0.01$), indicating inefficiencies in application. The study concludes that enhancing lablab productivity requires coordinated interventions: improving seed systems, promoting sustainable agronomic practices, expanding extension services and irrigation access, and improving input use efficiency.

Keywords – Determinants, Lablab Crop, N Tanzania, Productivity, Smallholder farmers

1. INTRODUCTION

Lablab (*Lablab purpureus*), also known as hyacinth bean, is a versatile leguminous crop that has gained increasing recognition worldwide for its resilience in harsh environments and multifaceted utility in food, feed, and soil fertility enhancement. Globally, leguminous crops such as soybeans, lentils, and beans contribute significantly to food

security, nitrogen fixation, and climate resilience. According to (FAO, 2021), pulses, including lablab, contribute to the dietary needs of over 2 billion people and serve as a vital protein source, especially in low- and middle-income countries. Lablab stands out among legumes due to its exceptional drought tolerance, ability to thrive in marginal soils, and wide range of applications, including consumption (as green pods, dry seeds, or leaves), animal fodder, green manure, and intercropping for soil fertility improvement (Hailu & Tolessa, 2020; Maass et al., 2010). While Asia and Africa have long incorporated lablab into traditional cropping systems, with India leading global production at over 200,000 hectares (ICRISAT, 2020), its cultivation remains underexploited across the regions. In Tanzania, lablab has emerged as a promising crop for improving food security, particularly in semi-arid zones such as Dodoma, Singida, Arusha, and Manyara. These regions experience frequent droughts and poor soil fertility, which limit the performance of conventional crops like maize and beans (URT, 2022).

The primary objective of the study was to examine the determinants of lablab productivity among smallholder farmers in Arusha, Manyara, Singida, and Dodoma regions. The specific objectives are: (i) to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of lablab farmers; (ii) to identify the major constraints affecting lablab productivity; and (iii) to estimate the effect of selected variables on the ordered levels of lablab productivity using an ordinal logistic regression model. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology, including study area description, research design, sampling procedures, and analytical methods; Section 3 presents the results covering socio-demographic characteristics, production constraints, and determinants of productivity; Section 4 discusses the findings in relation to existing literature; and Section 5 provides conclusions and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Empirical studies have confirmed lablab's potential as a dual-purpose crop that enhances food security and farm income. According to Maass et al. (2010), reported yield potentials of up to 4 tons per hectare can be achieved under favourable conditions, with biomass valued for livestock feeding. In Uganda, Otieno et al. (2018) found that lablab intercropping increased maize yields by 25% while boosting soil nitrogen levels. In Kenya, lablab fetched prices between Ksh 60–120/kg, depending on demand and post-harvest quality (Kamau et al., 2020). Similarly, Njau et al. (2020) documented lablab use by Tanzanian smallholder farmers for both fodder and household consumption and sale, while observing a lack of organized marketing channels. Northern and Central Tanzania are semi-arid regions characterized by low rainfall (400–1200 mm/year), high evapotranspiration, and fragile soils (URT, 2022). These conditions constrain traditional staple crops, making lablab an increasingly viable alternative. Despite its potential, persistently low yields reflect complex agronomic, institutional, and socio-economic constraints, including inadequate access to quality seed, escalating fertilizer prices, erratic weather, pests and diseases, and limited extension support (Mboya et al., 2022; Ngugi et al., 2022). While legumes such as common beans and cowpeas have been the focus of numerous productivity studies (Adugna & Menkir, 2021; Maredia et al., 2020), empirical evidence specific to lablab remains scarce (CIAT, 2023; Mboya et al., 2022). Previous research has often aggregated legume crops, masking crop-specific peculiarities and ignoring localized socio-environmental factors. Additionally, most studies employ binary logit models that dichotomize productivity, thereby losing information on ordinal gradations in output.

This study deploys ordinal logistic regression to preserve the ordered nature of productivity categories, offering a refined analytical lens for understanding how various factors contribute to different productivity levels. The primary objective of the study was to examine the determinants of lablab productivity among smallholder farmers in Arusha, Manyara, Singida, and Dodoma regions. The specific objectives are: (i) to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of lablab farmers; (ii) to identify the major constraints affecting lablab productivity; and (iii) to estimate the effect of selected variables on the ordered levels of lablab productivity using an ordinal logistic regression model. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology, including study area description, research design, sampling procedures, and analytical methods; Section 3 presents the results covering

socio-demographic characteristics, production constraints, and determinants of productivity; Section 4 discusses the findings in relation to existing literature; and Section 5 provides conclusions and policy recommendations.

2.1. Literature survey

2.1.1. Theoretical and conceptual frameworks

2.1.1.1. Theoretical framework

This study is guided by two complementary theoretical perspectives: **Institutional Theory (IT)** and **Rogers' (1963) Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DIT)**. Institutional Theory, widely applied in sociology and organizational studies, provides critical insights into how institutions, social structures, norms, and rules shape both individual and organizational behaviour. It posits that actors often conform to institutional norms and pressures to gain legitimacy and trust from stakeholders, even without critically questioning them (Lammers *et al.*, 2014). This theory emphasizes the influence of contextual forces, making it especially valuable for understanding how government policies, cultural norms, market regulations, and institutional arrangements affect farmers' decision-making and market participation. Within the context of this study, IT serves as a lens for examining how institutional elements such as agricultural policies, extension systems, market regulations, and value chain governance either facilitate or hinder lablab productivity among smallholder farmers. However, its focus on institutional stability over change and its limited attention to individual agency necessitate complementing it with a more innovation-centred perspective (Morris, 2014). To address this theoretical limitation, the study also draws on Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DIT), which explains how innovations are adopted and spread within a social system. DIT categorizes adopters into five groups: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards, each influenced by distinct motivational factors (Rosário *et al.*, 2022).

Innovators and early adopters are typically motivated by direct benefits and are more open to experimentation, whereas the early and late majority tend to rely on peer experiences. Laggards, on the other hand, require substantial persuasion and support to adopt new practices. In the context of lablab productivity, DIT offers a framework for understanding how different farmer groups perceive and adopt improved production techniques, post-harvest practices, and market linkages. It also sheds light on the roles of communication channels, demonstration effects, and peer influence in shaping adoption patterns. By integrating IT and DIT, the study captures both macro-level institutional influences and micro-level behavioural dynamics, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the lablab production process. While IT frames the exploration of how policy environments, institutional strategies, and governance structures influence market access and resource allocation, DIT explains how these institutional conditions intersect with individual-level adoption decisions. Together, these theories inform the design of strategies to promote lablab production through coherent policies, strengthened institutions, targeted extension services, and farmer-centred innovation dissemination.

2.1.1.2. Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework for this study integrates Institutional Theory and Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations Theory to analyse the productivity of lablab among smallholder farmers in Tanzania. It explains how background variables such as sex, marital status, education level, and main occupation influence productivity by affecting technology adoption and resource allocation. Government policies play an essential role, with positive effects through subsidies that reduce input costs, food safety standards that enhance marketability, and land tenure security that encourages investment. However, inconsistent or poorly implemented policies create uncertainty and discourage investment, thereby impeding production. Extension services are necessary for advancing production by improving farming techniques and market access, yet insufficient or poorly targeted services restrict farmers' access to necessary information and resources, limiting their productivity. Institutional strategies, such as strengthening value chains and improving market linkages, enhance production by facilitating better market access and expanding economic

opportunities. Conversely, weak institutional coordination results in fragmented value chains and restricted market access, negatively affecting production. Technological advancements significantly impact productivity by improving efficiency and product quality, boosting market competitiveness. However, high technology costs and infrastructure deficiencies pose barriers to adoption and limit production potential. Supportive policies and effective institutional frameworks mediate these relationships by facilitating strategy implementation and fostering agricultural development. Conversely, weak frameworks and poor communication can obstruct the effective application of policies and the adoption of new practices, thus constraining productivity.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework Diagram that illustrates the Determinants of Lablab Productivity

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Recent local studies indicate that lablab is gradually being integrated into farming systems due to its resilience, high biomass productivity, and income generation potential (Mponda et al., 2021; Njau et al., 2020). However, despite these advantages, reliable data on production levels, market trends, and socio-economic significance remain sparse. Most farmers cultivate lablab on a small scale, primarily for household use or occasional sales, without formal market structures or value chain development. According to the Tanzania Agriculture Sector Development Programme (URT, 2021), over 80% of legumes grown in Tanzania are sold in unstructured markets, often characterized by price instability and minimal government support. Farmers frequently face fluctuating prices (up to 50% in a single season) and unreliable buyers, especially during peak harvest periods. Additionally, climate variability significantly affects productivity, as rainfall inconsistency hampers flowering and seed formation (FAO, 2023; URT, 2022). This study is crucial for understanding and enhancing lablab's role in Tanzania's food and economic systems. In the face of climate change, resource degradation, and food insecurity, lablab offers a viable alternative that aligns with national and global goals, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 1, 2, and 13), which focus on ending poverty,

achieving food security, and combating climate change. Moreover, lablab aligns with Tanzania's national agricultural development priorities, including the Agricultural Sector Development Strategy (ASDS II), which advocates for promoting climate-smart crops, value addition, and market integration.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY OR METHODS

4.1. Description of the study area

The study was conducted in four regions of Tanzania (Dodoma, Singida, Manyara, and Arusha), which were purposively selected to represent diverse climatic conditions and their prominence in lablab production. Arusha Region, located in the volcanic highlands, is characterized by moderate to high rainfall, with annual precipitation ranging from 800 to 1,000 mm (URT, 2021). It benefits from a bimodal rainfall pattern that supports two cropping seasons annually (URT, 2021). Temperatures in Arusha vary from approximately 15°C in the cooler highland zones to about 28°C in lower altitudes (URT, 2021). Manyara Region, also in the northern zone, falls within the semi-arid Agro-ecological classification. It experiences variable and generally limited rainfall, typically ranging from 500 to 800 mm per year. Temperatures range from 18°C to 32°C, resulting in frequent water stress and climatic unpredictability that adversely affect agricultural productivity (URT, 2021). In the central zone, Dodoma Region lies on the central plateau and is characterized by a hot, dry climate with unimodal rainfall averaging around 500-700 mm annually. The region frequently experiences prolonged dry spells, with temperatures ranging from 20°C to 32°C, making it one of the driest areas in the country (URT, 2021). Singida Region, also located in the central zone, is situated in a marginal Agro-ecological area with low and erratic rainfall, generally between 450 and 700 mm per year. High evapotranspiration rates further reduce effective soil moisture availability, posing a significant constraint to consistent crop production. Temperatures in Singida typically range from 19°C to 31°C (URT, 2021). Although official statistics on lablab production remain limited, existing studies indicate relatively high adoption rates in Arusha (80.2%) and Manyara (66.3%) compared to Kilimanjaro (58.4%) and Morogoro (20.1%) (Minde *et al.*, 2023). Dodoma and Singida were selected due to lablab's growing use as animal feed and its compatibility with local farming systems in these regions (Missanga *et al.*, 2021).

4.2. Research design

This study adopted a cross-sectional research design, which involves the collection of data at a single point in time from diverse groups and locations. This design was particularly suitable given the time constraints of the study and the objective of capturing variations in lablab productivity and its determining factors among smallholder farmers across the four selected regions. The cross-sectional approach enabled meaningful comparisons of socio-economic, institutional, and biophysical variables across distinct Agro-ecological zones and farming communities (Wang & Cheng, 2020). To ensure a holistic understanding of the factors influencing lablab productivity, the study integrated both quantitative and qualitative methods (Allmark, 2004). Furthermore, the design facilitated the identification of key determinants of productivity through statistical analysis, specifically using ordinal logistic regression, which allowed for the classification of lablab productivity into ordered outcome categories.

4.3. Study population, sampling procedures, and sample size

The target population consisted of smallholder lablab farmers residing in Arusha, Manyara, Dodoma, and Singida regions. A multistage sampling technique was adopted. Firstly, the four regions were purposively selected based on their relevance to lablab cultivation and agro-ecological diversity. Secondly, within each region, one district and one ward within the district, as well as villages, were selected based on lablab production intensity and accessibility. Finally, farmers were randomly selected from village lists of lablab household farmers. A total of 200 lablab household farmers were randomly selected from the list of villages' lablab household farmers across the regions: (Dodoma = 48), (Singida=20), (Manyara = 58), and (Arusha =74), and finally involved in the data collection exercise.

4.4. Data collection

A mixed methods approach was adopted whereby both quantitative and qualitative data were collected from lablab farming households and other key informants. The quantitative data were collected through a structured household questionnaire. Qualitative data were obtained via focus group discussions (FGDs) with smallholder farmers and extension agents in each region. Each group comprised 8 participants, thus making a total of 32 members, including males and females involved in lablab production. The discussions were conducted using FGD guides. In addition, key informant interviews (KIIs) were conducted with representatives from the Ministry of Agriculture, regional agricultural offices, NGOs, lablab salesmen, and Agro-dealers, and the Agriculture Research Institute (TARI) distributed across the four regions. Interview guides were used to standardize the conversations. The integration of these methods enabled triangulation, improving the credibility and depth of the study findings (Singh et al., 2021). According to Gray (2014), combining different methods compensates for the limitations of each and enhances the overall robustness of the research. In addition to peer-reviewed literature, grey literature such as government policy documents and NGO reports was used to capture up-to-date and context-specific information not yet available in academic publications.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Data analysis

The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistical methods to analyse the data collected from smallholder lablab farmers across Arusha, Manyara, Dodoma, and Singida regions. The analysis was structured to address each specific objective of the study and to identify the key determinants of lablab productivity.

5.1.1. Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the socio-demographic and farm-level characteristics of respondents. Measures such as frequencies and percentages were calculated to present variables like age, education level, farm size, years of farming experience, access to extension services, input use, and market participation. These statistics provided a general profile of the sample and were instrumental in identifying trends and patterns across different regions and farming systems.

5.1.2. Ordinal logistic regression analysis

To address the core objective of identifying determinants of lablab productivity, the study adopted ordinal logistic regression (OLR). This method is appropriate when the dependent variable (lablab productivity) is ordinal, that is, categorized into ordered levels such as low, medium, and high productivity (Kumari *et al.*, 2016). OLR preserves the natural ordering of the response variable and improves the explanatory power of the model. The model estimated the influence of several independent variables grouped into socio-economic and agronomic factors on the likelihood of a farmer achieving higher levels of lablab productivity (Alemu, 2015). The proportional odds assumption was tested to validate the use of OLR.

Mathematical Equation adapted:

$$\log(P(Y < j)) / (P(Y > j)) = \alpha_j - (\beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5) \text{ for } j=1, 2$$

Where: α_j = The category-specific intercepts (thresholds), βX = The regression coefficients for each predictor.

Variables and Measurement.

Table 1: Operationalised dependent and independent variables adopted in the ordinal logistic regression model

Variable	Description	Measurement / Type	Expected Sign
Lablab productivity	Ordered level of production (Outcome)	Ordinal (1 = low to 4 = high)	—
Education level	Formal schooling attained	Categorical (None, Primary, Secondary, Tertiary)	±
Farming experience	Years engaged in farming	Ordinal (1 = 0–10 yr; 2 = 11–20; 3 = 21–30; 4 = 31+)	±
Farm size	Hectare under lablab	Ordinal (1 = <0.5; 2 = 0.5–2; 3 = 2–4; 4 = >4)	±
Labor availability	Adequate labour access	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Weather condition	Favourable rainfall pattern	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Market access	Ease of reaching buyers	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Improved seed	Use of certified varieties	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Soil fertility	Perceived soil adequacy	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Access to credit	Formal or informal loans	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Crop rotation	Rotating lablab with other crops	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Extension services	Receipt of advisory visits	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Fertiliser use	Application of chemical/organic fertiliser	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	+
Pests and diseases	Incidence during season	Binary (1 = Yes, 0=No)	–

5.1.3. Qualitative data analysis

Qualitative data from key informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs) were analysed using thematic content analysis. Transcripts were coded manually to identify recurring themes related to production constraints, market access, institutional support, and perceptions of lablab productivity. The findings were used to complement and validate the quantitative results, offering deeper insights into the underlying factors affecting productivity and adoption practices.

5.2. Discussion

This study examined the determinants of lablab productivity among smallholder farmers in northern and central Tanzania. The discussion interprets the findings in relation to the three specific objectives and situates them within broader agricultural development literature in sub-Saharan Africa.

5.2.1. Socio-demographic characteristics of Lablab Farmers

5.2.1.1. Sex dynamics in Lablab production

The sex composition of respondents shows a pronounced dominance of male participation in lablab farming, accounting for 74.5% of the sample compared to 25.5% female representation. This imbalance reflects persistent sex disparities in agricultural participation, which may be influenced by unequal access to critical production resources such as land, credit, extension services, and decision-making forums. Okiror et al. (2021) report that sexed norms in East African legume value chains are associated with women's representation in cash crop production. Similarly, Mnimbo et al. (2017) observed that men's higher involvement in value chains often coincides with greater access to institutional support services, including extension delivery and adoption of improved legume technologies, potentially contributing to this pattern.

However, in some communities, cultural norms allocate cash crop farming primarily to men while women focus on subsistence crops and household food provision (FAO, 2023). Household labour allocation patterns, seasonal migration, and childcare responsibilities may further limit women's participation. In addition, differences in market

orientation, mobility, and membership in farmer groups could shape participation rates (Njuki & Mburu, 2022). These findings suggest that sex disparities in lablab farming are multifaceted, requiring interventions such as sex-inclusive extension, capacity-building for female farmers, and facilitation of women’s participation in producer organizations and market platforms (Platform, 2024). Without such interventions, lablab productivity may exacerbate existing sex inequalities.

5.2.1.2. Age distribution and youth participation

The age profile indicates that lablab farming is mainly practiced by older adults, with 49.5% aged between 37 and 54 years and 25% aged 55–72 years, while only 23% fall within the youth category (18–36 years). This pattern may reflect broader youth disengagement from agriculture in Tanzania and sub-Saharan Africa; a trend linked to multiple structural barriers. According to Tijani (2022), limited access to land, capital constraints, weak mentorship opportunities, and negative perceptions of farming as a career are contributing factors. It is also possible that older farmers dominate lablab production because the crop’s long-term market prospects and agronomic familiarity align more with their accumulated farming experience and lower livelihood mobility. Younger people may prefer off-farm income opportunities in urban centres or crops with quicker returns (Afande et al., 2023). Such dynamics suggest the need for targeted youth engagement strategies in lablab value chains, such as promoting youth-led agribusiness models and integrating lablab into climate-smart livelihood programs.

5.2.1.3. Education and knowledge transfer

A large majority of respondents (88%) had completed only primary education, with 3.5% reaching secondary and 1.5% tertiary education, while 7% reported no formal education. This educational profile may influence the uptake of improved agronomic practices, market engagement, and the use of agricultural information technologies. According to Hassan and Knight (2023), found that higher education levels are associated with greater adoption of improved legume practices. However, practical experience, peer learning, and local knowledge may partially offset low formal education in influencing production decisions (Sinyolo & Mudhara, 2021). This suggests that extension systems should be adapted for low-literacy audiences through participatory learning, demonstration plots, visual aids, and the use of local languages (Tomlinson & Rhiney, 2018). Strengthening community-based platforms such as farmer field schools could further promote knowledge transfer and improve productivity.

5.2.1.4. Livelihood diversification and land use patterns.

The results indicate that 54% of respondents rely solely on crop farming, while 42.5% combine crop and livestock production. Only 3.5% diversify into off-farm income activities. This suggests that most households are highly dependent on agriculture, though some integrate mixed farming as a risk-buffering strategy. Aweke et al. (2023) report that mixed farming is associated with enhanced resilience and food security in drought-prone areas. Land ownership patterns reveal that 84% of respondents have 4 hectares or less, with 72.5% allocating 2 hectares or less to lablab. Such small land sizes may limit scalability and mechanization potential, a concern echoed by Mayele et al. (2024). However, small plots may also reflect a strategic choice to allocate land to multiple crops, balancing household food needs and market opportunities (Makoi et al., 2023).

Table 2: Description of the respondent’s socio-demographic characteristics (n = 200)

Number of farmers per region							
Variable	Class	Arusha	Manyara	Singida	Dodoma	Total	Percentage
Sex	Male	53	43	13	40	149	74.5
	Female	21	15	7	8	51	25.5
Age (Years)	18 – 36	19	12	0	15	46	23
	37 – 54	29	31	20	19	99	49.5
	55 – 72	25	14	0	11	50	25

	73+	1	1	0	3	5	2.5
Education Level	No formal	12	2	0	0	14	7
	Primary	59	52	20	45	176	88
	Secondary	2	2	0	3	7	3.5
	Tertiary	1	2	0	0	3	1.5
Occupation	Crop farming	41	33	9	25	108	54
	Crop & livestock farming	31	23	10	21	85	42.5
	Crop farming & Others	2	2	1	2	7	3.5
	Marital status	Single	8	8	0	2	18
	Married	66	50	20	46	182	91
Farming Experience (Years)	0 – 10	18	17	0	24	59	29.5
	11 – 20	2	16	1	9	28	14
	21 – 30	20	15	18	9	62	31
	31+	34	10	1	6	51	25.5
Total Owned Land (Ha)	<2	46	29	0	9	84	42
	5 – 4	16	23	20	25	84	42
	4+	12	6	0	14	32	16
Land under lablab (Ha)	0 – 0.4	6	11	20	3	40	20
	0.4 – 2	59	44	0	42	145	72.5
	2.4 – 4	4	1	0	2	7	3.5
	4+	5	2	0	1	8	4
Experience growing lablab	1 – 3	9	34	4	27	74	37
	4 to 6	40	6	0	12	58	29
	6+	25	18	16	9	68	34

5.3. Constraints affecting Lablab production

Table 3 presents constraints affecting lablab productivity among smallholder farmers across the four study areas. The findings point to multiple challenges in lablab production, spanning agronomic, economic, climatic, and infrastructural factors. The most commonly reported constraint was the prevalence of pests and diseases (84.5%), aligning with findings by Ogecha et al. (2019), who documented similar challenges in East African legume systems. Likewise, Popoola et al. (2020) found that pests remain a leading cause of yield losses in underutilized legumes across sub-Saharan Africa. While this may suggest a strong role of biotic stress, it is also possible that farmers perceive pests and diseases as a primary constraint because of their visible and immediate effects, while underlying factors like soil fertility decline or delayed planting may also contribute. Addressing this constraint may require integrated approaches that consider both technical management and farmers' knowledge and perceptions. The above is supported by observations from the Focus Group Discussion, as shown in the quote below.

“As farmers, we see pests and diseases as one of the biggest challenges in lablab production, affecting the crop from the field all the way to storage. In our areas, there are no specific chemicals or pesticides known to work effectively against lablab pests, so we end up buying whatever is available at the Agro-shops to try and save our crops. Sometimes these pesticides help to reduce the intensity of the problem, but do not provide total control; often, they don't work at all. We spend a lot of money without seeing good results, and even after spraying, the pests remain, continuing to damage our crops. What we really need is proper research to identify the exact pests attacking lablab and to recommend the right, effective control measures. This would help us reduce unnecessary costs and improve our yields” (FGD Dodoma, Singida, Manyara, and Arusha, April 2025)

Seed accessibility challenges, noted by 83% of respondents, are consistent with previous observations of weak seed systems for underutilized legumes (Minde et al., 2021). Farmers reported the use of the same seed that was previously stored after harvesting; the seeds are characterized by poor germination and are prone to diseases. However, the association between low adoption of improved lablab seed and production outcomes may also be influenced by preferences for local varieties with familiar taste, cooking quality, and storage traits; reliance on recycled seed to reduce expenditure; trust in known seed sources; and limited exposure to improved varieties (Breen et al., 2024; Letting et al., 2022). Transaction costs and timing mismatches between seed availability and planting windows further shape these patterns. These findings suggest that seed system improvements could be more effective if paired with participatory varietal development, decentralized distribution, and targeted information campaigns to build farmer confidence.

Also, information reported from the Focus Group Discussion

“Right now, one of our biggest challenges in lablab production is that we keep using recycled seed. Over time, the yields have gone down because the seeds no longer germinate well and are often attacked by diseases. We did receive improved seeds from an NGO, and we were told to multiply them and share them with our neighbours. But it has taken a long time to get another supply of improved seeds. The way we produce seeds here in the village is not the same as how the official seed production institutions do it, so in the end, the seeds we pass on are thought to be improved, but in reality, the quality has already dropped,” (Singida Region, April 2025).

High fertilizer prices, cited by 75.5% of respondents, were associated with reduced uptake, in line with previous studies linking high input costs to lower adoption levels (Getachew, 2019; Jayne & Sanchez, 2021). However, evidence from other contexts indicates that adoption decisions may also be shaped by perceptions of profitability, exposure to seasonal price fluctuations, access to credit, and risk tolerance (Ren et al., 2023; Sanogo, 2022; Yesuf & Köhlin, 2021). These associations may suggest that affordability is only one dimension of the challenge, and that financial and informational support may also play important roles in determining fertilizer use.

Information from the Focus Group Discussion;

“Accessing subsidised fertiliser is difficult due to complicated and time-consuming procedures. Farmers must travel from their villages to town, which incurs significant costs in both time and money for the journey there and back. Additionally, the amount of fertiliser farmers can purchase often depends on the funds they have available, affecting how regularly they can obtain and apply it on their farms. The process becomes even more challenging during the planting season because of the high demand and frequent internet connectivity issues reported by suppliers. As a result, farmers often spend entire working days traveling to Babati town and returning the next day, sometimes without successfully obtaining the fertiliser,” (Riroda Ward, Manyara Region, April 2025).

Climate variability, reported by 61.5% of respondents, aligns with the vulnerability of rain-fed lablab systems to seasonal rainfall fluctuations (Ariom, 2022). However, this association may also reflect farmers’ attribution of yield changes to weather conditions, even in cases where management practices contribute significantly to productivity variation. This suggests that climate adaptation strategies might be most effective when combined with improved agronomic planning and decision-support services to help farmers better interpret and act on climate information.

Table 3: Major Constraints Affecting Lablab Production

Number of Household Lablab Growers (n=200)											
Variables	Category	Arusha		Dodoma		Manyara		Singida		Total	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Inaccessibility of quality seed	Yes	64	38.6	48	28.9	54	32.5	0	0	166	83
	No	10	29.4	0	0	4	11.8	20	58.8	34	17.0

Higher fertilizer cost	Yes	64	42.4	32	21.2	50	33.1	5	3.3	151	75.5
	No	10	20.4	16	32.6	8	16.3	15	30.6	49	24.5
Irrigation Problem	Yes	45	40.9	16	14.6	42	38.2	7	6.4	110	55.0
	No	29	32.2	32	35.6	16	17.8	13	14.4	90	45.0
Limited access to labour	Yes	45	50.5	7	7.9	33	37.1	4	4.5	89	44.5
	No	29	26.1	41	36.9	25	22.5	16	14.4	111	55.5
Weather Condition	Yes	48	39.0	23	18.7	43	35.0	9	7.3	123	61.5
	No	26	33.8	25	32.5	15	19.5	11	14.3	77	38.5
Pests and Diseases	Yes	68	40.2	27	16.0	54	32.0	20	11.8	169	84.5
	No	6	19.4	21	67.7	4	12.9	0	0	31	15.5
Lack of storage facilities	Yes	45	40.9	9	8.2	41	37.3	15	13.6	110	55.0
	No	29	32.2	39	43.3	17	18.9	5	5.6	90	45.0
Limited Land Size	Yes	45	43.7	11	10.7	40	38.8	7	6.8	103	51.5
	No	29	29.9	37	38.1	18	18.6	13	13.4	97	48.5

5.4. Determinants of Lablab productivity

Table 4 presents the results of an ordinal logistic regression model examining factors influencing lablab productivity among smallholder farmers. The model was estimated using data from 200 observations. Also, provides critical insights into factors influencing lablab productivity. The model was statistically significant overall ($p < 0.000$), with a pseudo-R-squared value of 0.17, which is acceptable for cross-sectional data in socio-economic research when the number of factors is significant (Ozili, 2023).

5.4.1. Significant positive determinants

The use of improved lablab seed was the variable most strongly associated with higher productivity ($\beta = 3.575$, $p < 0.01$). This pattern aligns with earlier studies showing that access to certified and improved seed varieties is linked to better yield potential and resistance to pests, diseases, and climatic stressors (Ojiewo et al., 2018). However, this association could also be influenced by farmer characteristics such as being more commercially oriented, having greater access to markets, or possessing stronger institutional linkages that simultaneously increase the likelihood of using improved seed and achieving higher yields. This finding aligns with Diffusion of Innovations Theory, which posits that early adopters and innovators are more likely to embrace new technologies that offer clear advantages, thereby influencing others through demonstration effects (Rogers, 1963). The uptake of improved seed also reflects Institutional Theory's emphasis on how institutional arrangements such as seed certification systems, input supply networks, and supportive policy measures shape technology availability and adoption patterns. Crop rotation was also a significant positive predictor of lablab productivity ($\beta = 2.318$, $p < 0.01$). This aligns with existing literature showing that rotational practices disrupt pest and disease cycles, enhance soil fertility, and improve water retention. Kumar et al. (2019) demonstrated that incorporating legumes in rotational systems increases nitrogen availability and reduces dependence on chemical fertilizers. However, the observed association cannot be interpreted as causal, as more productive farmers may also be more likely to adopt crop rotation due to greater resource availability, such as land or better access to extension advice. From an Institutional Theory perspective, this practice is often facilitated by extension recommendations and agricultural guidelines embedded within institutional frameworks.

Also, from a Diffusion of Innovations perspective, crop rotation adoption can be seen as an innovation diffused through farmer-to-farmer learning and extension demonstrations. Similarly, pest and disease management practices were significantly associated with higher productivity ($\beta = 2.518$, $p = 0.02$), underscoring the potential benefits of integrated pest management (IPM). This resonates with findings by Nyangau et al. (2020), who reported that IPM adoption among smallholder legume farmers in East Africa led to improved yields and reduced losses. Nonetheless, whether these practices directly improved productivity or whether higher productivity incentivized their adoption

could include unobserved variables such as farmer education, access to credit, or prior exposure to training programs, which may simultaneously influence both pest management and yields. This aligns with Institutional Theory, which highlights the role of structured extension programs and policy-led pest control initiatives in enabling farmers to adopt these practices. Likewise, the Diffusion of Innovations Theory explains the gradual spread of such practices from innovators, who test and refine control methods, to the early and late majority through knowledge sharing and observed benefits. Favourable weather conditions were also found to significantly enhance lablab productivity ($\beta = 0.861, p = 0.048$), corroborating the findings of Mpogole et al. (2020), who identified climatic stability as a critical determinant of productivity in rain-fed agricultural systems.

Adequate and well-distributed rainfall, coupled with optimal temperature ranges, supports vigorous plant growth and reduces the risk of stress-related yield losses. The relationship was captured through farmers' perceptions reflecting their immediate experiences of seasonal climatic conditions, though longer-term climatic trends were beyond their scope. However, higher-productivity farmers may be more likely to adopt climate-adaptive practices due to better resources or extension access. Unobserved variables such as education, credit access, or prior training may also explain part of the lablab productivity. Although weather is a contextual rather than institutional factor, Institutional Theory underscores how institutions mediate farmers' adaptive responses to climate variability through policy interventions, extension advice, and climate information services. Within the Diffusion of Innovations framework, the adoption of practices in response to weather patterns can also spread through social networks, influencing overall productivity.

5.4.2. Negative association with fertilizer use

Interestingly, fertilizer use had a significant negative association with productivity ($\beta = -1.613, p < 0.01$). This counterintuitive finding could be attributed to inappropriate or excessive application of inorganic fertilizers, which may not align with lablab's nutrient requirements. As noted by Chianu et al. (2012) and Vanlauwe et al. (2014), improper input use among smallholder farmers often results from limited extension services and a lack of context-specific agronomic knowledge. Additionally, farmers applied DAP fertilizer during planting and supplemented it with ammonium sulphate (SA) during crop growth, both of which are rich sources of nitrogen and contribute to soil nitrogen levels. Since lablab is a leguminous crop capable of fixing atmospheric nitrogen, its response to either excessive or insufficient nitrogen-based fertilizers may be limited (Adem et al., 2021). This explains the gaps in institutional guidance, limited policy emphasis on crop-specific nutrient management, and weak regulation of fertilizer recommendations and quality. Also, reflects incomplete or distorted diffusion of correct agronomic practices where innovators and early adopters may apply fertilizers appropriately, but these practices are not effectively communicated to, or are misinterpreted by, the early and late majority. The above is supported by observations from the Focus Group Discussion and Key Informant Interviews, as shown in the quote below.

"Extension services are not available at the field as we often receive theoretical advice during village meetings, which is often challenging for us to fully understand and apply the information without practical, hands-on demonstrations. Much of the advice is too general and sometimes does not even address lablab, which is the crop we are focusing on. As a result, we frequently make our own decisions, such as combining organic and inorganic fertilisers based on what we think is best. Also, due to limited knowledge, we may apply fertiliser in areas that do not need it, leading to wastage or even soil damage. What we really need are soil testing services, clear guidance on the exact type and quantity of fertiliser to use, and practical, crop-specific training that can help improve our farming practices," (FGD Manyara April 2025).

"Lablab has traditionally been grown as a subsistence crop, although in recent years it has gained commercial value. However, it is not yet included among the seventeen strategic crops that typically benefit from subsidy programs, including subsidised fertilizers. As a result, farmers often take advantage of subsidy opportunities intended for other crops and use inputs that are sometimes not specific to or suitable for lablab" (KII Manyara Regional Agricultural Office, April 2025).

5.4.3. Non-significant variables

Other socio-economic variables, including education level, farming experience, land size, labour availability, market access, soil quality, access to credit, and extension services, were not statistically significant. These findings mirror results by Khumalo et al. (2024), who argued that while such variables are generally important for agricultural productivity, their effects may be indirect or context-dependent, particularly in subsistence systems where resource constraints limit the realisation of their full benefits.

Table 3: Ordinal logistic regression model results for the determinant of lablab productivity level

Lablab Productivity	Coef.	St. Err.	p-value
Education	0.098	0.357	0.785
Farming experience	0.144	0.137	0.296
Farm Size	0.296	0.23	0.198
Labor Availability	-0.153	0.403	0.705
Weather	0.861**	0.436	0.048
Market Access	0.386	0.432	0.372
Improved seed	3.575***	0.731	0.000
Soil	0.295	0.204	0.148
Access to Credit	0.222	2.023	0.913
Crop rotation	2.318**	0.691	0.001
Extension services	0.828	0.908	0.362
Fertilizer user	-1.613***	0.432	0.000
Pest and diseases	2.518**	1.08	0.02
Number of obs	200		
Prob > chi2	0.000		
Pseudo R-squared	0.17		
Log likelihood	-190.765		

statistically significant level*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

5.5. Market, utilization, and sales patterns

5.5.1. Multifunctional utilization

As illustrated in Figure 1, the findings indicate that lablab plays a multifunctional role within smallholder farming systems, with a significant proportion (94.5%) of respondents reporting production primarily for commercial purposes. This pattern points to a broader trend of engagement with market-oriented legume production, which may reflect shifting livelihood strategies in response to evolving socio-economic and agroecological conditions. The observed orientation toward commercialization is consistent with principles derived from **Rogers’ Diffusion & Innovation Theory (DIT)**, which suggests that farmers are more likely to adopt agricultural innovations when they perceive them to offer relative advantage, compatibility with existing practices, and observable outcomes (Rogers, 1963). In this context, lablab’s adaptability to dryland conditions, soil fertility enhancement potential, and emerging market value appear to align with factors that often support innovation uptake in resource-constrained farming environments. These findings are in line with observations by Missanga et al. (2021), who observed that smallholder farmers in drought-prone regions of Tanzania are increasingly adopting lablab as a business crop due to its adaptability and growing demand. However, despite the commercial emphasis, 32% of respondents continue to cultivate lablab for household consumption, underscoring its persistent significance in food and nutrition security strategies.

This continued subsistence function may be interpreted through **Institutional Theory (IT)**, which emphasizes the role of normative structures, cultural practices, and institutional frameworks in shaping and stabilizing behaviour

over time (Scott, 2014). The continuing presence of lablab in household diets may reflect embedded livelihood systems wherein farmers integrate both market and consumption objectives, particularly in contexts where food access remains uncertain. This interpretation is supported by Glatzel et al. (2025), who highlight lablab's contribution to dietary diversity and its nutritional importance during periods of seasonal food scarcity. At the same time, the reported commercial orientation may partly reflect the influence of development programs, extension services, or policy interventions that promote lablab as a viable market crop. In such cases, the emphasis on commercialization may represent a response to institutional encouragement rather than a fully autonomous transition. Furthermore, social desirability bias cannot be discounted, as farmers may report market-oriented behaviour in ways that align with perceived expectations from external stakeholders or researchers. Such responses may not always correspond with actual sales volumes, profitability, or market integration.

Also, the study focused on regions with relatively established lablab production, which may possess more favourable agroecological conditions, stronger institutional presence, or better access to input and output markets. As such, the findings may not be readily generalizable to regions where lablab is less established, or where farmers face different structural constraints. According to Shadish et al. (2002), the need to account for context-specific factors when assessing the applicability of research findings beyond the study area.

Figure 1: Utilization of Lablab by respondents

5.5.2. Market access and trade linkages

Results show that an overwhelming 97.5% of lablab produce is marketed locally within the region of production, predominantly through informal channels. This heavy reliance on proximal market networks underscores the limited integration of smallholder farmers into broader, structured markets. The pattern is consistent with findings by Neupane et al. (2024), who reported that most legume producers face significant barriers in reaching higher-value urban markets due to weak transportation logistics and limited bargaining power. Also, results show that lablab produce is marketed locally within the region of production, predominantly through informal channels. This heavy reliance on proximal and unstructured market networks highlights a key limitation in the business pathway: the restricted market reach and lack of integration into broader, formalized value chains. This pattern resonates with findings by Neupane et al. (2024), who reported that legume producers across sub-Saharan Africa often struggle to access higher-value urban markets due to inadequate transportation infrastructure, limited access to market information, and weak bargaining power. While earlier findings in this study suggest a strong commercial orientation among lablab producers (94.5%), the localized nature of marketing reveals that commercialization remains primarily constrained within informal economies.

This apparent contradiction reinforces the utility of combining Diffusion Innovation Theory (DIT) and Institutional Theory (IT) in interpreting adoption behaviours. From the DIT perspective, the uptake of lablab as a

market crop may be influenced by perceived relative advantages; however, structural and institutional constraints may inhibit full integration into formal markets. Informal transactions may persist not simply due to preference but as a result of embedded institutional realities, such as the absence of organized cooperatives, weak buyer networks, or poor rural infrastructure. Moreover, the dominance of localized sales raises questions about the depth and sustainability of the commercialization process. While farmers may identify economic motivations for growing lablab, their limited access to distant or higher-value markets suggests that commercial intent does not always translate into economic empowerment. Also, it may include temporary project-based incentives, localized demand flows, or the influence of external actors encouraging market production without facilitating access to formal buyers.

Figure 2: Lablab Market channels and trade linkages

5.5.3. Seasonal marketing patterns

The findings reveal a pronounced seasonal pattern in lablab marketing, with 81.5% of respondents reporting sales during the peak harvest period between July and September. While this aligns with the natural production cycle of the crop, it also underscores the limited flexibility within the value chain for most smallholder farmers. This temporal concentration restricts income-generating opportunities and may increase farmers' exposure to market saturation and price volatility. According to Alawode and Chiamaka (2024), poorly diversified marketing calendars among smallholders are closely linked to heightened susceptibility to income shocks and unstable market conditions. When considered alongside the predominantly localized and informal nature of lablab sales, this seasonal constraint further reflects structural limitations in market access and weak integration into broader value chains. Despite 94.5% of farmers indicating commercial intent in lablab production, the convergence of temporal and spatial marketing constraints points to a form of commercialization that remains shallow and institutionally restricted. These patterns are consistent with the tenets of Institutional Theory, which highlights how entrenched informal systems, limited post-harvest infrastructure, and inadequate policy frameworks shape and often constrain farmer behaviour.

While Innovation Diffusion Theory helps explain farmers' adoption of lablab based on perceived benefits such as drought tolerance and market potential, Institutional Theory more effectively accounts for the persistent barriers that limit full participation in formal, diversified, and geographically dispersed markets. Also, the observed seasonality in marketing may be underpinned by buyer preferences during harvest periods, temporary price incentives, or farmers' reliance on local traders who operate seasonally.

Information from the Focus group discussion

"We sell the lablab crop immediately after harvesting because it is highly susceptible to pests. Furthermore, the cost of storage is too high, which forces us to sell quickly; we are also uncertain about the existence of a future market. So, due to this uncertainty and the lack of reliable traders, we are compelled to sell our produce immediately to the available

middlemen; only those with power in terms of storage and transportation can fetch a higher market price. (Itwaswi ward- Dodoma region April 2025)

Furthermore, the cross-sectional nature of this study limits the ability to assess how marketing behaviours evolve or respond to external changes, such as policy shifts or market interventions. Consequently, it remains unclear whether the observed marketing pattern reflects a stable strategy or a context-specific adaptation. Additionally, since the study focuses on established lablab-producing regions, the generalizability of the findings to less-developed production zones may be limited

Figure 1: Seasonal marketing patterns

6. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

Based on the study's findings and conclusion, the following evidence-based recommendations are proposed to improve lablab productivity among smallholder farmers in Tanzania.

- Given the strong positive association between improved seed use and lablab productivity, national agricultural policy should prioritize investments in seed system development. This includes supporting the multiplication and distribution of drought-tolerant, high-yielding, and pest-resistant lablab varieties through public-private partnerships and localized seed networks.
- The productivity benefits linked to crop rotation highlight the need for intensified agricultural extension efforts. Training programs should emphasize soil health management, crop sequencing, and other sustainable practices to improve yields and long-term land productivity.
- Pests and diseases were identified as key constraints. Therefore, the development and dissemination of crop-specific IPM packages for lablab integrating biological controls, timely field monitoring, and safe pesticide use should be prioritized by extension services and research institutions.
- The negative correlation between fertilizer use and productivity suggests issues with application practices or input quality. Training programs should provide lablab-specific guidance on fertilizer types, dosages, and timing, ensuring farmers apply inputs effectively and avoid economic losses or soil degradation.

7. CONTRIBUTIONS TO SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Areas for Further Study

- Further study should focus on exploring the agronomic requirements of lablab under rainfed conditions, considering its potential to enhance soil nitrogen and crop yields.
- Lablab is mainly cultivated for commercial purposes. However, its market access remains localized and seasonal; future research should investigate opportunities for value addition in enhancing its commercialization.

8. CONCLUSION

Based on the study findings, it can generally be concluded that lablab production is predominantly male-dominated and primarily undertaken by middle-aged to older farmers, most of whom have attained only primary education. Cultivation typically occurs on small plots, with production largely oriented toward commercial purposes. However, market access remains limited, highly localized, and seasonal, thereby constraining the full commercialization potential of the crop. It can also be concluded that lablab productivity is impeded by a range of interrelated agronomic, institutional, and economic challenges. Chief among these are pest and disease pressures, high fertilizer costs, limited access to quality seed, and inadequate irrigation infrastructure, factors that collectively undermine efforts to enhance yield and scale up production. It is further concluded that results from the ordinal logistic regression model identified five variables that significantly influence lablab productivity: the use of improved seed, crop rotation, pest and disease management, weather conditions, and fertilizer use. The positive effects of improved seed and crop rotation highlight the critical role of sustainable, knowledge-based agronomic practices in improving productivity. Similarly, effective pest and disease control, along with favourable weather conditions, were found to be key contributors to increased yields. Lastly, it is concluded that the negative relationship between fertilizer use and productivity may reflect issues such as misapplication, inappropriate timing, or low input quality.

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REFERENCES

- Adem, A., Mekuriaw, Y., & Asmare, B. (2021). Effects of accessions and fertilizer levels on agronomic characteristics, forage biomass yield, and nutritive value of lablab (*Lablab purpureus* L) under irrigation in dry lands of Ethiopia. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2021.1943202>
- Adujna, A., & Menkin, A. (2021). Improving legume productivity in sub-Saharan Africa: Statistical modelling approaches. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 16(2), 55–68.
- Afande, F. O., Maina, W. N., & Maina, M. P. (2023). *Youth preferences in agribusiness: Evidence from emerging value chains in East Africa*. *African Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 19(2), 101–118.
- Alawode, A., & Chiamaka, O. T. (2024). Linking structured commodity markets with formal agricultural finance to improve value chain transparency and inclusion. *International Journal of Advanced Research Publication and Reviews*, 1(4), 87-109.
- Alemu, T. (2015). Determinants of wheat yield variation of smallholders in South Eastern Ethiopia: application of ordered logistic regression. *Science, Technology and Arts Research Journal*, 4(3), 61-66.
- Allmark, P. (2004). Should research samples reflect the diversity of the population? *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 30(2), 185-189.
- Ariom, T. O., Dimon, E., Nambeye, E., Diouf, N. S., Adelusi, O. O., & Boudalia, S. (2022). Climate-smart agriculture in African countries: A Review of strategies and impacts on smallholder farmers. *Sustainability*, 14(18), 11370.

- Aweke, A., Tefera, T., Gezahegn, M., & Sileshi, M. (2023). Determinants of household choice of livelihood diversification strategies in selected drought-prone areas of the southern nationalities and peoples' region, Ethiopia. *Agricultural Sciences*, 14(10), 1375-1392.
- Breen, J., Mponda, O., & Mabagala, R. B. (2024). Farmers' preferences and constraints to the adoption of improved legume varieties in East Africa. *Journal of Agricultural Innovation and Development*, 12(1), 55-67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaid.2023.11.004>
- Centre for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) (2023). *Harnessing underutilized legumes for food and climate resilience*. International Center for Tropical Agriculture.
- Chianu, J. N. & Mairura, F. (2012). *Mineral fertilizers in the farming systems of sub-Saharan Africa. A review*. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 32, 545-566.
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2021). *The state of food and agriculture 2021: Making agrifood systems more resilient to shocks and stresses*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://www.fao.org/publications>
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2023). *Gender and agriculture: Closing the knowledge gap*. FAO. <https://www.fao.org>
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2023). *Pulse crops and climate change: The future of resilient legumes*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Getachew, T. (2019). Pulse crops production opportunities, challenges, and their value chain in Ethiopia: A review article. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 9(1).
- Glatzel, K., Nuhu, S., & Temu, A. (2025). *Enhancing food and nutrition security through legume diversification: The case of lablab in Tanzania*. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 92, 33-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2025.03.002>
- Gray, D. E. (2014). *Doing research in the real world* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Hailu, G., & Tolessa, D. (2020). The role of lablab (*Lablab purpureus*) in enhancing food and feed security in drought-prone areas. *International Journal of Agronomy and Agricultural Research*, 17(3), 45-53.
- Hassan, B. A., & Knight, J. (2023). Adaptation to climate change and variability by farming households in North-Central Nigeria. *Sustainability*, 15(23), 16309.
- International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT) (2020). *Harnessing the potential of lablab in dryland farming systems*. <https://www.icrisat.org>
- Jayne, T. S., & Sanchez, P. A. (2021). *Input subsidies and soil fertility in Africa: A review of evidence and lessons*. *Food Policy*, 101, 102054. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2021.102054>
- Kamau, J., Mutuku, J. M., & Ochieng, M. A. (2020). Value chain analysis of underutilized legumes: A case study of lablab in Kenya. *Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development*, 12(7), 97-104.
- Khumalo, N. Z., Mdoda, L., & Sibanda, M. (2024). Uptake and Level of Use of Climate-Smart Agricultural Practices by Small-Scale Urban Crop Farmers in eThekweni Municipality. *Sustainability*, 16(13), 5348. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16135348>
- Kumar, S., Meena, R. S., Datta, R., Verma, S. K., Yadav, G. S., Pradhan, G., & Mashuk, H. A. (2019). Legumes for carbon and nitrogen cycling: an organic approach. In *Carbon and nitrogen cycling in soil* (pp. 337-375). Singapore: Springer Singapore.
- Kumari, V., Agrawal, R. & Kumar, A. (2016). Use of ordinal logistic regression in crop yield forecasting. *MAUSAM*, 67(4), 913-918.
- Lammers, J. C., Atouba, Y. C., & Carlson, E. J. (2014). Institutional theory. *The International Encyclopedia of Organizational Communication*, 1-21.
- Letting, D. K., Wekesa, E., & Ouma, J. (2022). *Factors influencing farmers' seed sourcing and varietal preferences in Kenya: A case of lablab bean*. *African Crop Science Journal*, 30(4), 435-448. <https://doi.org/10.4314/acsj.v30i4.6>
- Maass, B. L., Knox, M. R., Venkatesha, S. C., Angessa, T. T., Ramme, S., & Pengelly, B. C. (2010). Lablab purpureus – A crop lost for Africa? *Tropical Plant Biology*, 3, 123-135.

- Makoi, J. H. J. R., Mtengeti, E. J., & Mwaseba, D. L. (2023). Smallholder crop diversification and food security in Tanzania. *Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics*, 15(4), 120–132. <https://doi.org/10.5897/JDAE2023.1350>
- Maredia, M. K., Reyes, B., & Mihiretu, Y. (2020). Agricultural productivity of grain legumes in Africa: A comparative analysis. *World Development Perspectives*, 20, 100269.
- Mayele, J. M., Kolleh, J. B., & Saburi, J. E. (2024). The impacts and causes of land fragmentation on farm productivity: Case review of East African countries. *Open Journal of Ecology*, 14(5), 455–482.
- Mboya, R. M., Kimaro, A. A., & Mligo, C. (2022). Challenges and opportunities of underutilized legumes in Tanzania: A case of lablab (*Lablab purpureus*). *African Crop Science Journal*, 30(1), 95–110.
- Mboya, R. M., Nchimbi-Msolla, S., & Chove, B. (2022). The role of indigenous legumes in sustainable agriculture. *Journal of Applied Agricultural Science and Technology*, 4(1), 14–25.
- Minde, J. J. (2023). Potential of underutilized Dolichos lablab (*Lablab purpureus*) seeds in improving nutritional quality and livelihood in Tanzania [Master's thesis, Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST)].
- Minde, J. J., Venkataramana, P. B., & Matemu, A. O. (2021). Dolichos Lablab-an underutilized crop with future potentials for food and nutrition security: a review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 61(13), 2249–2261.
- Missanga, J. S., Venkataramana, P. B., & Ndakidemi, P. A. (2021). Recent developments in Lablab purpureus genomics: a focus on drought stress tolerance and use of genomic resources to develop stress-resilient varieties. *Legume Science*, 3(3), e99.
- Mnimbo, T.S., Lyimo-Macha, J., Urassa, J.K. (2017). Influence of sex on roles, choices of crop types, and value chain upgrading strategies in semi-arid and sub-humid Tanzania. *Food Sec.* 9, 1173–1187 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-017-0682-2>
- Morris, M. W. (2014). Values as the essence of culture: Foundation or fallacy? In M. Yuki & M. W. Morris (Eds.), *Multi-level issues in organizational behavior and strategy* (Vol. 5, pp. 31–47). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Mpogole, H., Dimoso, P., & Mayaya, H. (2020). Agriculture for rural development in Tanzania. TEMA Publishers Co. Limited, Dar es Salaam.
- Mponda, O., Kapinga, R., & Mcharo, T. (2021). Farmer perspectives on underutilized legumes in central Tanzania. *Tanzania Journal of Agricultural Development*, 7(2), 85–94.
- Neupane, N., Shakya, S., Koirala, S., & Khadka, M. (2024). Identifying Market Challenges and Opportunities in Mixed Farming System Piloted Sites of the Mid-hills Of Nepal: The Khotang Case.
- Ngugi, M., Muriuki, J., & Ochieng, J. (2022). Challenges and opportunities in marketing underutilized crops in East Africa. *African Journal of Agricultural Marketing*, 3(4), 51–63.
- Njau, F., Mbwaga, A. M., & Ndakidemi, P. A. (2020). Adoption and performance of lablab in Tanzanian farming systems. *African Journal of Rural Economy and Development*, 9(1), 22–31.
- Njuki, J., & Mburu, S. (2022). Gendered participation and empowerment in agricultural value chains. In J. Njuki & E. Waithanji (Eds.), *Transforming Gender and Food Security in the Global South* (pp. 89–108). Routledge.
- Nyangau, P., Muriithi, B., Diiro, G., Akutse, K. S., & Subramanian, S. (2020). Farmers' knowledge and management practices of cereal, legume, and vegetable insect pests, and willingness to pay for biopesticides. *International Journal of Pest Management*, 68(3), 204–216. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09670874.2020.1817621>
- Ogecha, J. O., Nyende, A. B., & Adipala, E. (2019). Constraints to legume production in East Africa: A case study of Kenya and Uganda. *African Journal of Plant Science*, 13(7), 167–175. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJPS2019.1785>
- Ojiewo, C. O., Rubyogo, J. C., Wesonga, J. M., Bishaw, Z., Abang, M. M., & Gelalcha, S. W. (2018). Mainstreaming efficient legume seed systems in Eastern Africa: challenges, opportunities and contributions towards improved livelihoods. FAO.

- Okiror, J. J., Ekere, W., & Barungi, M. (2021). Gender dynamics in legume value chains in Eastern Africa. *African Journal of Rural Development*, 6(2), 15–26.
- Otieno, D., Onyango, M., & Ouma, G. (2018). Effect of legume intercropping on maize yield and soil fertility in Western Kenya. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 13(12), 611–617.
- Ozili, P. K. (2023). The acceptable R-squared in empirical modelling for social science research. In *Social research methodology and publishing results: A guide to non-native English speakers* (pp. 134-143). IGI Global.
- Platform, C. G. I. (2024). Advancing sex equality and women's empowerment in agri-food systems: Research-based recommendations.
- Popoola, J., Ojuederie, O., & Omonhinmin, C. (2020). Neglected and Underutilized Legume Crops: Improvement and. *Recent advances in grain crops research*, 123.
- Ren, C., Chen, X., & Liao, Y. (2023). *Understanding fertilizer use decisions under market volatility: Evidence from smallholder farms in Asia and Africa*. *Agricultural Systems*, 203, 103456. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2022.103456>
- Rogers, E. M. (1963). *Diffusion of innovations* (1st ed.). Free Press.
- Rosário, A., Oliveira, B., Figueiredo, M., & Veloso, A. (2022). Diffusion of innovations theory: A review of implementation in education and ICT. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(3), 3655–3676. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10702-w>
- Sanogo, D. (2022). *Credit access and input adoption among smallholder farmers in West Africa*. *Journal of Rural Finance and Agricultural Economics*, 6(3), 211–229.
- Scott, W. R. (2014). *Institutions and organizations: Ideas, interests, and identities* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Shadish, W. R., Cook, T. D., & Campbell, D. T. (2002). *Experimental and quasi-experimental designs for generalized causal inference*. Houghton Mifflin.
- Singh, R., Sharma, P., & Verma, K. (2021). Research methods and their applications in social sciences. *International Journal of Social Research*, 15(2), 101–115.
- Sinyolo, S., & Mudhara, M. (2021). Agricultural training and technology adoption among smallholders. *Development Southern Africa*, 38(6), 859–874. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0376835X.2021.1939159>
- Tijani, F. O. (2022). *Factors Influencing Young People's Career Choice in Agriculture from the Educational Perspective: A Case Study of Kwara State, Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, Newcastle University).
- Tomlinson, J., & Rhiney, K. (2018). Assessing the role of farmer field schools in promoting pro-adaptive behaviour towards climate change among Jamaican farmers. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*, 8(1), 86–98.
- United Republic of Tanzania (URT) (2021). Region's socio-economic profile. National Bureau of Statistics.
- United Republic of Tanzania (URT) (2021). *Agriculture Sector Development Programme Phase II (ASDP II) Midterm Review Report*. Ministry of Agriculture, Government of Tanzania.
- United Republic of Tanzania (URT) (2022). *Agriculture Sector Development Programme Phase II (ASDP II)*. Ministry of Agriculture, Dar es Salaam.
- United Republic of Tanzania (URT) (2022). *Tanzania climate-smart agriculture profile: Dodoma, Singida, Arusha, and Manyara regions*. Ministry of Agriculture and FAO.
- Vanlauwe, B., Coyne, D., Gockowski, J., Hauser, S., Huising, J., Masso, C., & Sanginga, N. (2014). *Sustainable intensification and the African smallholder farmer*. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 8, 15–22.
- Wang, X., & Cheng, Z. (2020). Cross-sectional studies: strengths, weaknesses, and recommendations. *Chest*, 158(1), S65-S71.
- Yesuf, M., & Köhlin, G. (2021). *Farmers' risk preferences and adoption of agricultural technologies in Ethiopia*. Environment for Development Discussion Paper Series, EfD DP 21-02.